

Reduced-Order Model of Ammonia Decomposition Reaction for Increasing Nuclear Thermal Rocket Performance

Elia Puccinelli^{a*} and Angelo Pasini^a

^a Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

* Corresponding Author

Abstract

In the history of nuclear propulsion, hydrogen has always been considered the first choice as a propellant due to its overwhelming performance, which overshadows the problems related to its storage difficulty and low density; however, the versatility of nuclear propulsion systems, which do not depend on the chemical reaction between two substances to generate thrust, allows the use of a large variety of fluids as propellants. One of the most cited in the literature is ammonia. Using ammonia as a propellant can simplify system design thanks to the easiness of storability, but comes with the drawback of less than halved specific impulse compared to hydrogen. A solution to bridge this performance gap for the NH₃-fed nuclear thermal propulsion systems is to exploit the decomposition of ammonia. The decomposition of ammonia is an endothermic reaction, thanks to which two molecules of ammonia divide into three molecules of hydrogen and one of nitrogen. A mixture of nitrogen and hydrogen has a molecular weight equal to half that of ammonia. Given the dependence of the specific impulse on the inverse root of the molar mass, achieving complete decomposition of the ammonia before it escapes from the nuclear reactor allows for greatly increasing the specific impulse. Nevertheless, ammonia decomposition is a reaction with very slow kinetics and is inhibited by the high pressures generally found inside the channels of the nuclear reactor; for this reason, it is not trivial to reach the ammonia complete decomposition exploiting only the high temperature of the flow cooling the reactor core. The present work introduces an innovative configuration of an ammonia nuclear propulsion system where a catalyst is inserted in the initial part of the coolant channels of a particle bed reactor to achieve ammonia flow cracking through the combination of catalysis and thermolysis; the catalysis effect is fundamental to accelerate the reaction kinetics and making the reaction time comparable with the flow residence time inside the channel. The paper presents a steady-state one-dimensional model for the endothermic reaction of ammonia on a bed of catalyst and nuclear fuel layered coated mixed particles releasing heat toward the propellant flow. The model allows for estimating the degree of ammonia cracking achieved at the exit of the proposed nuclear reactor configuration and the corresponding performance gain. Achieving complete ammonia decomposition is crucial to bring the performance of ammonia-fed nuclear thermal propulsion above that of the best chemical propulsion systems.

Keywords: Decomposition; Ammonia; NTP; NEP; Thermochemistry

Nomenclature

A = cross section area
 C = species concentration
 C_h = Stanton number
 $C_{NH_3}^{(S)}$ = concentration of ammonia on the particles surface
 c_p = specific heat
 D_p = particle diameter
 E_a = reaction activation energy
 G = bed load
 h_{conv} = convective heat transfer coefficient
 h_t = flow total enthalpy
 K = reaction equilibrium constant
 k = thermal conductivity
 k_o = Arrhenius constant
 \mathcal{M} = molar weight
 \dot{m} = mass flow rate

\dot{n} = molar flux per unit volume
 N_s = activation site density
 Nu = Nusselt number
 p = pressure
 Re = Reynolds number
 R_{univ} = gas universal constant
 \dot{q}''' = coolant channel power density
 \dot{q}_{prop}''' = propellant heat input per unit volume
 r = radius
 \dot{r} = reaction rate
 Pr = Prandtl number
 S = control volume surface
 T = temperature
 u = velocity
 \dot{V}_{prop} = propellant volumetric flow
 $\Delta H_{r,o}$ = heat of reaction
 ε = porosity
 λ = reaction advancement parameter
 μ = viscosity
 ν = stoichiometric coefficient
 ρ = density
 τ = viscous force per unit surface

Subscripts

ex= external layer
f= fuel kernel
j= j-th element
p= particle
t=stagnation property
w= particle external surface

Acronyms/Abbreviations

NTR= Nuclear Thermal Rocket
rds= rate determining step

1. Introduction

The great heritage of hydrazine monopropellant propulsion systems [1,2] has demonstrated how it is possible, thanks to the use of a catalytic particle bed axially crossed by the propellant flow, to achieve ammonia decomposition in thrusters with low flow residence times. Previous works carried out by the nuclear propulsion team of the University of Pisa [3,4] have described how ammonia represents an excellent alternative to hydrogen for use as a propellant in Nuclear Thermal Rockets (NTR), especially considering the increase in performance given by its decomposition. Ammonia has the great advantage of being non-cryogenically storable at ambient conditions, of having a density almost ten times higher than that of hydrogen, and of being present as an In-Situ resource on the Moon [5–7]; these advantages are however overshadowed by the reduced performance that ammonia promises, namely a specific impulse of about 370 s [3] which is lower than that of the best chemical propulsion systems. However, achieving complete ammonia cracking before exiting the propulsion system would increase specific impulse by approximately 15-20%, making the performance of systems using ammonia as a propellant equal to or superior to that of chemical propulsion systems using cryogenic propellants. The major advantage of ammonia cracking is the ability to have a monopropellant propulsion system that can rely on the ISRU and does not require complex storage systems, ensuring the same level of performance as cryogenic-based bipropellant systems. To this end, it is essential to develop a propulsion system in which the ammonia flow can achieve complete decomposition. The ammonia decomposition reaction is shown in Eq. (1)

Ammonia decomposes endothermically into hydrogen and nitrogen (stoichiometric ratio of 3:1) requiring a reaction enthalpy of 92.44 kJ mol⁻¹. The reaction kinetics can be accelerated by using a catalyst. Ammonia decomposition has been widely investigated for the production of green hydrogen at ambient conditions on Earth, and, in the literature, there is a lot of information on which are the best catalysts for enhancing this process [8–15]. Based on the principle of microscopic reversibility [16], catalysts that are effective in the synthesis of ammonia (a well-known process in the chemical industry, known as the Haber-Bosch process [11]) should also be effective in the dissociation of ammonia. The best catalysts for splitting the ammonia molecule are those composed of the following metals: Ru, Fe, Cu, Ni, Ir, Mo, Co, Pt, Pd, and Rh. Among all, ruthenium stands out as the best one [11]. However, in industrial processes, other materials are often preferred due to the ruthenium rarity and the difficulties and environmental impact of its extraction. Among the ones listed above, the main one is nickel [11,17]. Several experiments with different catalysts have shown that Ni is one of the most effective materials for the ammonia decomposition reaction, with an activity that varies according to the material used as the supporting base and eventual doping materials, such as La or K [18]. One of the main drawbacks of using Ni instead of Ru for the ammonia decomposition in the energetic industry is the higher temperature required (500-600°C instead of the 400°C required by Ru), but this aspect is negligible for applications inside a nuclear reactor. One of the most common support material for the Nickel catalyst is certainly alumina [11]. In presence of a catalyst, the reaction reported in Eq. (1) can be broken down into a series of intermediate steps [19]. The following Eq.(2)-(8) represent these steps, where * indicates a vacant site on the catalyst surface.

Accordance to [9], these steps are widely accepted in the literature, however, there is uncertainty on which of them is the rate determining step (rds) of the reaction chain. The confusion for the rds is mainly because it depends on the conditions in which the decomposition is taking place: temperature, pressure, the type of catalysts material, the type of support material, and the presence of doping materials. The most adopted rds are two: the removal of hydrogen atoms from the ammonia molecule (steps (3)-(5)), called also N-H bond cleavage, and the N desorption and recombination of nitrogen molecule (steps (6) and (7)). In some cases, found for example with the Ru catalyst, the limiting phenomenon can also be the desorption of hydrogen from the catalyst surface (step (8)); such cases are referred as hydrogen poisoning of the catalyst since most of the active sites are covered by hydrogen which does not allow the dissociation of the ammonia molecules to proceed. Generally, monometallic catalysts can accelerate only one of the two processes (i.e. metals that have high N-binding energy can easily break the N-H bond, but at the same time, the desorption of N from the catalyst becomes very slow); a solution to accelerate the kinetics of the two rate-limiting steps is to use bimetallic catalysts, in which one metal has high N-binding energy while the other has a low one [20–22]. One of the most efficient bimetallic catalysts is Ni-Pt [23]. Ru, Ni, and Ni-Pt emerge from literature as

the most attractive materials for the catalyst's active phase. To select the best catalyst for application in the NTP system under consideration, we must focus on two fundamental aspects: the contribution that the material can make in enhancing the kinetics of the reaction, linked to the activation energy that the material makes necessary to activate the reaction mechanism, and its maximum operating temperature, linked to its melting point.

2. Analyzed Configuration

In the studied case, the catalyst will be inserted inside the channels of a nuclear reactor with particle bed fuel, differentiated from the classic configurations present in the literature [24] thanks to the axial crossing of the particle bed by the propellant flow, rather than radial [4]. In this way, the nuclear fuel will provide the energy required for the dissociation reaction (and the increase in flow temperature) while the catalyst will accelerate its kinetics. The use of a layered particle fuel allows the catalyst to be mixed with the nuclear fuel, providing the system with a configuration very similar to that of classic monopropellant thrusters. Since the reactor channels present a strong axial temperature gradient (from 400 K at the inlet to 3000 K at the outlet), it is also important to identify the best position for the catalyst inside the channel to avoid subjecting the catalytic material to operating temperatures that it cannot tolerate. Fig. 1 shows the coolant channel's configuration.

Fig. 1: Nuclear Reactor's Coolant Channel Composition

Among the identified catalysts, nickel presents the most stringent constraints in terms of activation energy and operating temperature, as visible from the properties in Table 1. Introducing a catalyst with an active Ni phase into the analysis, therefore, allows us to study a sort of worst-case scenario for the decomposition of ammonia, useful for determining whether complete decomposition of the propellant can also be achieved in this configuration.

Table 1: Ammonia Catalyst Active Phases Properties

Material	E_a (kJ/mol)	T_{melt} (K)	Ref.
Ru	75-130	1728	[19]
Ni	70-290	2607	[19]
Ni-Pt	47	1728	[23]

Following the results reported in the previous analyses [3], a suitable positioning of the catalytic bed could be in the first third of the channel length, to keep the operating temperature below 1700 K. One of the most used supports for the active nickel phase in catalysts is alumina (Al_2O_3) [11], which also provides good structural properties, necessary to allow an adequate operational life for the catalytic pellets in a high-stress environment such as that of a nuclear reactor channel.

The assumed nuclear reactor model is shown Fig. 2 [4], and its channels are characterized by a power density profile that follows the trend of the one represented in Fig. 3, obtained through neutron analysis using the Monte Carlo code OpenMC [25].

The power density profile generated inside the channels is influenced by the amount of catalyst inserted inside them; nickel is a strong neutron absorber and causes a reduction in the intensity of the particle flux generating fission events inside the reactor channels with a consequent lowering of the intensity of the generated power density profile. Moreover, since the particle fraction inside the channels is limited to the maximum value of about 0.6 [26], to insert the catalyst pellets in a configuration with maximized particle fraction, it is necessary to remove fuel particles: this further reduces the intensity of the power density inside the channels.

Fig. 2: Particle Bed Nuclear Reactor Layout

Multiphysics analyses, including neutronics, thermo-hydraulics, and thermochemistry of the reactor and of the propellant flow flowing in it, are necessary to determine the material and quantity of the catalyst that allows for obtaining a complete decomposition of the ammonia without poisoning the reactor (i.e., without having an excessive impact on the neutron budget). Such analyses must be performed iteratively and must also include burnup analyses to determine how the catalyst impacts the reactor's operational lifetime, as well as thermomechanical checks to ensure the survival of the catalyst particles within the channels. Obviously, performing such detailed coupled studies requires enormous computational cost and considerable time, which, while a necessary price for developing configurations with designs already at an advanced stage, is also detrimental for early-design-stage configurations that must undergo numerous modifications and upgrades. For this reason, it is important to propose simplified models for conducting such multiphysics analyses (or segments thereof) during the initial development of innovative systems. These models, at the expense of lower accuracy, allow for rapid design checks that identify critical points in the configurations and the aspects on which subsequent modifications should be focused. This work, focusing only on the thermochemistry segment, aims to propose a simplified methodology for determining the performance achievable by catalytically and pyrolytically decomposing ammonia flow within the channels of the NTP engine's nuclear reactor. The proposed model will then be used within a broader multiphysics analysis to determine the best configuration, from both a neutronic and propulsive standpoint, of the proposed modified particle bed reactor.

3. Methodology

The proposed model for the study of the decomposition of the ammonia flow inside the reactor channels does not focus on the neutron part and therefore assumes a fixed power density profile shown in Fig. 3 and obtained for a catalyst fraction equal to 30% inside the first 20 cm of the 60 cm long channel.

Fig. 3: Nuclear Reactor's Channel Power Density Axial Profile

Other important applied assumptions are:

- Steady state conditions.
- Quasi 1D flow.
- The catalyst and fuel pellets treated as an homogenous mixture heating the flow.
- The propellant flow at the nuclear reactor's coolant channel inlet is assumed to be composed only of ammonia in gaseous state ($T_o = 405\text{ K}$ and $p_o = 70\text{ bar}$).
- The catalyst inserted in the channel as Ni as the active phase and Al_2O_3 as the support.
- The propellant transport properties and the specific heats are function of the temperature according to the ideal contributions reported in [27–31]
- The particles do not exchange heat with the channel wall but only with the propellant flow.
- The most relevant species considered are NH_3 , N_2 e H_2 [14]
- The spatial uniformity of the flow across the particle bed is maintained
-

Fig. 4: Analyzed Coolant Channel Configuration

Fig. 4 shows the applied power density profile on the coolant channel as a boundary condition of the problem and the control volume on which the balancing equations for the propellant flow are applied. As already stated, assuming steady, 1D flow through the particle bed, the governing equations for the propellant flow can be written as:

Flow continuity:

$$\oint_S \rho \mathbf{u} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = 0 \rightarrow \frac{d(\rho u)}{dx} = 0 \rightarrow \rho u = G = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{NH}_3}^{(0)} \mathcal{M}_{\text{NH}_3}}{A_{\text{bed}}} \quad (9)$$

Species continuity:

$$\oint_S C_j \mathbf{u} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \int_V (v_j'' - v_j') \dot{r} dV \rightarrow \frac{d(C_j u)}{dx} \approx u \frac{dC_j}{dx} = (v_j'' - v_j') \dot{r} \quad (10)$$

Momentum:

$$\oint_S \rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \oint_S p d\mathbf{S} + \oint_S \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot d\mathbf{S} \rightarrow \rho u \frac{du}{dx} = \frac{dp}{dx} - \frac{dp_{\text{loss}}}{dx} \quad (11)$$

Energy:

$$\oint_S \rho h_t \mathbf{u} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \int_V \dot{q}_{prop}''' \rightarrow \rho u \frac{dh_t}{dx} = \dot{q}_{prop}''' \quad (12)$$

Assuming negligible velocity change ($\frac{du}{dx} \approx 0$), along the channel portion considered, the pressure losses of the flow can be estimated using the Ergun equation [32]:

$$\frac{dp}{dx} = - \left[\frac{150(1-\varepsilon)}{\rho u D_p} \mu + 1.75 \right] \frac{(1-\varepsilon) \rho u^2}{\varepsilon^3 D_p} \quad (13)$$

Moreover, using the relationship between the enthalpy and the flow's temperature and neglecting the variation of the propellant specific heat along the channel, the energy balance may be rewritten as:

$$\frac{dT_t}{dx} = \frac{h_{conv}(T_w - T_t)\pi\sqrt{2}}{\varepsilon D_p \rho u c_p} + \frac{\Delta H_{r,o} \dot{r}}{\rho u c_p} \quad (14)$$

Where h_{conv} can be estimated using the Stanton number (C_h):

$$h_{conv} = \rho u c_p C_h \quad (15)$$

With C_h defined as

$$C_h = \frac{Nu}{RePr} \quad (16)$$

While, by following the imposed assumptions, the particles external wall temperature can be determined using Eq.(17) [3]

$$T_w = T_t + \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3h_{conv} r_p^2} \quad (17)$$

With the particles internal and external layer temperatures that can be estimated, respectively, as [3]

$$T = + \frac{r_f^2}{6k_f} \dot{q}''' - \frac{r^2}{6k_f} \dot{q}''' + T_t + \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3h_{conv} r_p^2} + \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3k_{ex} r_f} - \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3k_{ex} r_p} \quad (18)$$

$$T = T_t + \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3h_{conv} r_p^2} + \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3k_{ex} r} - \frac{\dot{q}''' r_f^3}{3k_{ex} r_p} \quad (19)$$

Considering the ammonia decomposition global reaction:

The molar flux per unit volume of each species can be calculated using the following equations:

$$\dot{n}_{NH_3} = \dot{n}_{NH_3}^{(0)} + (v''_{NH_3} - v'_{NH_3})\lambda \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{n}_{H_2} = (v''_{H_2} - v'_{H_2})\lambda \quad (22)$$

$$\dot{n}_{N_2} = (v''_{N_2} - v'_{N_2})\lambda \quad (23)$$

Where λ is the reaction advancement parameter and constitute one of the unknown of the problem:

$$dC_j = \frac{d\dot{n}_j}{\dot{V}_{prop}} = \frac{v_j'' - v_j'}{\dot{V}_{prop}} d\lambda \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{d\lambda}{dx} = \frac{\dot{V}_{prop}}{v_j'' - v_j'} \frac{dC_j}{dx} \quad (25)$$

Combining the previous equation with the species continuity equation (Eq.(10)), the relation between the advancement parameter and the reaction rate is obtained:

$$\frac{d\lambda}{dx} = \frac{\dot{V}_{prop}}{u} \dot{r} \quad (26)$$

To close the problem, it is important to define a formulation for the reaction rate (\dot{r}). As described previously, the Eq.(1)-(8) represent the commonly accepted model for the ammonia decomposition reaction. The mechanism includes the ammonia chemisorption on the catalyst surface considering that the surface sites are energetically homogenous; this hypothesis allows for assuming that the adsorption of the species follows the Langmuir isotherm [33]. The reaction rate based on the assumption of Langmuir isotherm can be written as reported in Eq.(27).

$$\dot{r} = N_s k_o e^{-\frac{E_a}{R_{univ}T}} \frac{K C_{NH_3}^{(S)}}{1 + C_{NH_3}^{(S)}} \quad (27)$$

Following the work reported in [11,14,34], in cases with high pressures (over 1 bar) and low temperatures (for Ni, <1000 K), the Temkin–Pyzhev mechanism [34] can be adopted. This mechanism assumes as the rds the recombinative desorption of nitrogen, meaning that the reaction rate depends on the hydrogen partial pressure, following a power law formulation as the one reported in Eq.(28).

$$\dot{r} = k_o e^{-\frac{E_a}{R_{univ}T}} p_{NH_3}^\alpha p_{H_2}^\beta \quad (28)$$

The α and β varies according to the operating conditions of the catalyst, following the expression derivated in [34]. Currently, for simplicity of treatment, the values assumed were those shown in [34] and reported in Eq.(29), which, however, were ideal for slightly different operating conditions: in the subsequent iterations of the model, the values of the parameters required by Eq.(28) will be estimated for the precise operating conditions in which the catalyst will be found inside the nuclear reactor. For the purpose of the present work, which aims to provide a simplified model for the thermochemical analysis segment, the approximate values reported are an excellent starting point for estimating the degree of ammonia decomposition.

$$-\dot{r}_{NH_3} = (4.859 \times 10^8) e^{-\frac{E_a}{R_{univ}T}} \frac{p_{NH_3}^{0.73}}{p_{H_2}^{0.64}} \quad (29)$$

Finally, the partial pressures of the different species are calculated as follows:

$$p_{NH_3} = \frac{\dot{n}_{NH_3}}{\dot{n}_{NH_3} + \dot{n}_{H_2} + \dot{n}_{N_2}} p \quad (30)$$

$$p_{N_2} = \frac{\dot{n}_{N_2}}{\dot{n}_{NH_3} + \dot{n}_{H_2} + \dot{n}_{N_2}} p \quad (31)$$

$$p_{H_2} = \frac{\dot{n}_{H_2}}{\dot{n}_{NH_3} + \dot{n}_{H_2} + \dot{n}_{N_2}} p \quad (32)$$

While the activation energy E_a is assumed equal to 110 kJ/mol, a value in the middle of the range shown in Table 1, for the nickel. After the channel's region with the catalyst pellets, since the flow is still moving on a bed of particles, which are not presenting an active phase, the set of equations describing the flow properties and composition is maintained the same but the activation energy value is updated with the one of uncatalyzed ammonia decomposition reaction, i.e. $E_a=335$ kJ/mol.

4. Results

The model previously described included a system of ordinary differential equations to be integrated for determining the flow properties and composition along the coolant channel. The integration has been carried out numerically, using a Runge-Kutta method [35] and the results are shown in the following Fig. 5-Fig. 8.

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the particle external wall temperature and the gas mixture temperatures, respectively. The particles cooling is effective and their temperature does not exceed the limiting value of 3200 K, even in the kernel, while the temperature reached by the propellant at the channel exit is about 2935 K, a suitable value for a particle bed nuclear thermal propulsion system.

Fig. 5: Particles External Wall Temperature along the Channel Axis

Fig. 6: Propellant Flow Temperature along the Channel Axis

Pressure losses represent one of the main drawbacks of the configuration. The size of the particles inside the channel ($D_p=1.275$ mm) is such as to cause a total pressure drop of approximately 30 bar from the entrance to the exit of the bed, as shown in Fig. 7. This loss, while on the one hand helping to increase the residence time of the flow inside the catalytic bed, on the other hand would force the reactor feed pumps to work for a greater pressure drop, however this eventuality is avoided by using a specific propellant management system, illustrated in [36].

Fig. 7: Propellant Flow Pressure along the Channel Axis

Finally, the molar fraction of NH_3 , H_2 , and N_2 composing the flow along the channel are illustrated in Fig. 8. As visible, the assumed reaction rate and the hypothesized activation energy, inserted in the Arrhenius contribution of such rate, allows for obtaining a complete ammonia decomposition at the exit of the channel portion with the catalytic bed. The complete ammonia decomposition makes the exiting gas mixture composed of only hydrogen and nitrogen, causing an increase of the specific impulse.

Fig. 8: Propellant Flow Composition along the Channel Axis

The specific impulse has been estimated by assuming the same exit temperature and composition for the gas flow inside each one of the 37 channels of the reactor (a simplified assumption since, without any modification to the channels' composition, they will present different power density profiles [3]) and an expansion ratio equal to 100 for the integrated nozzles. The obtained specific impulse is about 445 s, an increment of the 15% respect to the case without ammonia decomposition. This value of specific impulse would make the proposed configuration giving the same level of performance of the best chemical propulsion system using LOx/LH_2 , but without the need to use cryogenic storage solutions.

As a final remark, Fig. 9 shows the ammonia molar fraction of the propellant flow along the channel axis obtained by integrating the system of ODEs using different values of activation energy inside the suggest range for the nickel catalyst and one last value for the uncatalyzed reaction. The obtained plots highlight how it is important to correctly determine the activation energy for the application considered since it greatly influences the final gas mixture composition and the specific impulse. In the worst-case scenario, the one with the $E_a = 335$ kJ/mol along the overall

particle bed, the decomposition level achieved at the end of the channel is around 60%, which gives an increase of the specific impulse equal to the 10%.

Fig. 9: Ammonia Molar Fraction along the Channel Axis as a Function of the Reaction Activation Energy

9. Conclusions

This work has introduced a simplified methodology for conducting thermochemical analyses to determine the composition and properties of the viscous, nonadiabatic, and chemically reacting propellant flow through the channels of a nuclear reactor in an NTP system. This analysis will constitute a segment of a larger multiphysics study aimed at determining the performance of the nuclear propulsion system. The simplicity of the model allows results to be obtained in a few seconds, an ideal approach for cases requiring multiple iterations between neutronics, thermohydraulics, thermochemistry, and thermomechanics of the configuration being developed. Obviously, the proposed model will require some improvements:

- The reaction rate will need to be calibrated to the specific operating conditions of the catalytic bed in the nuclear reactor, starting from the power law model with a more accurate estimate of the exponents α and β .
- The activation energy will need to be more precisely estimated for the application under consideration, following a fixed definition of the catalyst composition and its percentage within the particle bed in the channel. This percentage will depend on the coupling with the neutron analysis, as an excessive presence of nickel could have a severe effect on the neutron budget of the nuclear reactor.
- The presence of a heterogeneous catalyst (and therefore a mixture of gas and solid) can destroy the spatial uniformity given by the assumption of perfect mixing of the propellant flow on the catalytic bed. To verify this hypothesis, it is necessary to conduct a diffusion analysis to determine whether the concentrations of the chemical species evolve similarly both in the bulk of the flow and in the boundary layer region around the particles [37].
- The contribution of radiolysis (a decomposition reaction triggered by impinging photons on the ammonia molecule) must be included in the model, as it can give rise to an enhancing effect but also to competing reactions for the formation of free radicals.
- The heat exchange model must be expanded to include the conductive exchange between particles of different nature (nuclear fuel and catalyst) and the walls of the duct, and the radiative contribution to heating of the flow in the areas with high-temperature particles.

Although, as highlighted by the list just described, the model is based on strong assumptions, it can still be used, already at this stage, to obtain a rough estimate of achievable performance. With the assumed reaction rate formulation and with related activation energy values up to 130 kJ/mol, the particle bed is capable of causing complete decomposition of the propellant flow before it exits the channel, ensuring an increase in specific impulse of approximately 15% compared to the NTP using undecomposed ammonia as a propellant. This level of performance makes the use of ammonia for the NTP much more attractive, as it would guarantee superior performance to

chemical propulsion systems without the use of cryogenic substances and with a significant reduction in the overall size of the propulsion system.

Acknowledgements

The project leading to this paper has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme under agreement N° 101186520. BANter, Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket.

European
Innovation
Council

Funded by
the European Union

References

- [1] Evans, D. D., and Price, T. W., "The Status of Monopropellant Hydrazine Technology," 1968.
- [2] Makled, A. E., and Belal, H., "Modeling of Hydrazine Decomposition for Monopropellant Thrusters," 2009.
- [3] Puccinelli, E., Santana, S., Giusti, V., Pasini, A., and Thomas, D., "Analysis of Newly Designed NTP Particle Bed Reactor Coolant Channel Performance Enhanced by Ammonia Decomposition," presented at the 75rd International Astronautical Congress, IAC Milan, 2024.
- [4] Elia Puccinelli, Valerio Giusti, and Angelo Pasini, "Design of an Ammonia-Fed Nuclear Thermal Propulsion System for Reusable Space-Tug in Cislunar Orbits," presented at the NETS 2025, Huntsville, AL, U.S.A., 2025. <https://doi.org/10.13182/xyz-47430>
- [5] Nikitaev, D., and Dale Thomas, L., "Impacts of In Situ Alternative Propellant on Nuclear Thermal Propulsion Mars Vehicle Architectures," *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, 2022, pp. 1–15.
- [6] Nikitaeva, D., Smith, C. D., and Duchek, M., "Engine Cycle Comparison for Alternative Propellant Nuclear Thermal Propulsion Engines," presented at the ASCEND 2023, Las Vegas, Nevada, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2023-4715>
- [7] Kornuta, D., Abbud-Madrid, A., Atkinson, J., Barr, J., Barnhard, G., Bienhoff, D., Blair, B., Clark, V., Cyrus, J., and DeWitt, B., "Commercial Lunar Propellant Architecture: A Collaborative Study of Lunar Propellant Production," *Reach*, Vol. 13, 2019, p. 100026.
- [8] Kunsman, C. H., "The Thermal Decomposition of Ammonia on Tungsten, Molybdenum and Nickel. i," *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, Vol. 50, No. 8, 1928, pp. 2100–2113.
- [9] Ristig, S., Poschmann, M., Folke, J., Gómez-Cápiro, O., Chen, Z., Sanchez-Bastardo, N., Schlögl, R., Heumann, S., and Ruland, H., "Ammonia Decomposition in the Process Chain for a Renewable Hydrogen Supply," *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, Vol. 94, No. 10, 2022, pp. 1413–1425. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cite.202200003>
- [10] Shindo, H., Egawa, C., Onishi, T., and Tamaru, K., "Reaction Mechanism of Ammonia Decomposition on Tungsten," *Journal of the Chemical Society, Faraday Transactions 1: Physical Chemistry in Condensed Phases*, Vol. 76, 1980, pp. 280–290.
- [11] Lucentini, I., Garcia, X., Vendrell, X., and Llorca, J., "Review of the Decomposition of Ammonia to Generate Hydrogen," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, Vol. 60, No. 51, 2021, pp. 18560–18611. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.1c00843>
- [12] Mojtahedi, W., and Abbasian, J., "Catalytic Decomposition of Ammonia in a Fuel Gas at High Temperature and Pressure," *Fuel*, Vol. 74, No. 11, 1995, pp. 1698–1703.
- [13] Bradford, M. C., Fanning, P. E., and Vannice, M. A., "Kinetics of NH₃ Decomposition over Well Dispersed Ru," *Journal of Catalysis*, Vol. 172, No. 2, 1997, pp. 479–484.

- [14] Sayas, S., Morlanés, N., Katikaneni, S. P., Harale, A., Solami, B., and Gascon, J., "High Pressure Ammonia Decomposition on Ru–K/CaO Catalysts," *Catalysis Science & Technology*, Vol. 10, No. 15, 2020, pp. 5027–5035.
- [15] Zheng, W., Cotter, T. P., Kaghazchi, P., Jacob, T., Frank, B., Schlichte, K., Zhang, W., Su, D. S., Schüth, F., and Schlögl, R., "Experimental and Theoretical Investigation of Molybdenum Carbide and Nitride as Catalysts for Ammonia Decomposition," *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, Vol. 135, No. 9, 2013, pp. 3458–3464. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja309734u>
- [16] Tolman, R. C., "The Principle of Microscopic Reversibility," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, Vol. 11, No. 7, 1925, pp. 436–439. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.11.7.436>
- [17] Muroyama, H., Saburi, C., Matsui, T., and Eguchi, K., "Ammonia Decomposition over Ni/La2O3 Catalyst for on-Site Generation of Hydrogen," *Applied Catalysis A: General*, Vol. 443, 2012, pp. 119–124.
- [18] Okura, K., Okanishi, T., Muroyama, H., Matsui, T., and Eguchi, K., "Ammonia Decomposition over Nickel Catalysts Supported on Rare-Earth Oxides for the On-Site Generation of Hydrogen," *ChemCatChem*, Vol. 8, No. 18, 2016, pp. 2988–2995. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.201600610>
- [19] Spatolisano, E., Pellegrini, L. A., De Angelis, A. R., Cattaneo, S., and Roccaro, E., "Ammonia as a Carbon-Free Energy Carrier: NH₃ Cracking to H₂," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, Vol. 62, No. 28, 2023, pp. 10813–10827. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.3c01419>
- [20] Henpraserttae, S., Toochinda, P., and Charojrochkul, S., "The Development of Nickel Catalyst for Ammonia Decomposition," Thammasat University, 2018.
- [21] Takahashi, A., and Fujitani, T., "Kinetic Analysis of Decomposition of Ammonia over Nickel and Ruthenium Catalysts," *Journal of Chemical Engineering of Japan*, Vol. 49, No. 1, 2016, pp. 22–28.
- [22] Parker, L., "The Catalytic Decomposition of Ammonia," PhD Thesis. Cardiff University, 2019.
- [23] Chellappa, A. S., Fischer, C. M., and Thomson, W. J., "Ammonia Decomposition Kinetics over Ni-Pt/Al₂O₃ for PEM Fuel Cell Applications," *Applied Catalysis A: General*, Vol. 227, Nos. 1–2, 2002, pp. 231–240.
- [24] Haslett, R., "Space Nuclear Thermal Propulsion Program Final Report, Grumman Aerospace Corporation," PL-TR-95-1064, 1995.
- [25] Romano, P. K., and Forget, B., "The OpenMC Monte Carlo Particle Transport Code," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, Vol. 51, 2013, pp. 274–281.
- [26] Mughal, A., Chan, H. K., Weaire, D., and Hutzler, S., "Dense Packings of Spheres in Cylinders: Simulations," *Physical Review E*, Vol. 85, No. 5, 2012, p. 051305. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.85.051305>
- [27] Lemmon, E. W., and Jacobsen, R. T., "Viscosity and Thermal Conductivity Equations for Nitrogen, Oxygen, Argon, and Air," *International Journal of Thermophysics*, Vol. 25, No. 1, 2004, pp. 21–69. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:IJOT.0000022327.04529.f3>
- [28] Wei, C., Raad, S. M. J., Leonenko, Y., and Hassanzadeh, H., "Correlations for Prediction of Hydrogen Gas Viscosity and Density for Production, Transportation, Storage, and Utilization Applications," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Vol. 48, No. 89, 2023, pp. 34930–34944.
- [29] Gao, K., Wu, J., Bell, I. H., Harvey, A. H., and Lemmon, E. W., "A Reference Equation of State with an Associating Term for the Thermodynamic Properties of Ammonia," *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data*, Vol. 52, No. 1, 2023. Retrieved 28 November 2023. <https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jpr/article/52/1/013102/2881588>
- [30] Ojelade, O. A., and Zaman, S. F., "Ammonia Decomposition for Hydrogen Production: A Thermodynamic Study," *Chemical Papers*, Vol. 75, No. 1, 2021, pp. 57–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11696-020-01278-z>
- [31] Assael, M. J., Huber, M. L., Perkins, R. A., and Takata, Y., "Correlation of the Thermal Conductivity of Normal and Parahydrogen from the Triple Point to 1000 K and up to 100 MPa," *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data*, Vol. 40, No. 3, 2011. Retrieved 9 September 2025. <https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jpr/article/40/3/033101/242016>
- [32] Ergun, S., "Fluid Flow through Packed Columns," *Chemical engineering progress*, Vol. 48, No. 2, 1952, p. 89.
- [33] Boudart, M., and Djéga-Mariadassou, G., "Kinetics of Heterogeneous Catalytic Reactions," Princeton University Press, 2014.
- [34] Armenise, S., García-Bordejé, E., Valverde, J. L., Romeo, E., and Monzón, A., "A Langmuir–Hinshelwood Approach to the Kinetic Modelling of Catalytic Ammonia Decomposition in an Integral Reactor," *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, Vol. 15, No. 29, 2013, pp. 12104–12117.

- [35] Shampine, L. F., and Reichelt, M. W., "The MATLAB ODE Suite," *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, Vol. 18, No. 1, 1997, pp. 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1137/S1064827594276424>
- [36] Puccinelli, E., Giusti, V., and Pasini, A., "Lumped Parameter Analysis of Autogenous Propellant Pressurization System for Nuclear Thermal Rocket," *Nuclear Technology*, 2024, pp. 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295450.2024.2410637>
- [37] Sherwood, T. K., "Diffusion Phenomena in Heterogeneous Catalysis," *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, Vol. 10, No. 4, 1965, pp. 595–610. <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac196510040595>

DRAFT VERSION